

New advances in the understanding of Bulgarian geology through fission-track analysis – a review

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Abstract. The paper is focused on the development and application of fission-track analysis in Bulgaria from the first experiments in the 1980s to the present. The results from two different approaches (the conventional method and fission-track analysis using LA-ICP-MS), obtained for deciphering the thermal and tectonic evolution of several zones of the Balkanides, are summarized. They demonstrate the significance of the method and its considerable contribution to the understanding of Bulgarian geology.

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INTRODUCTION

Fission-track (FT) analysis is a low-temperature geochronological method used for dating geological events based on the accumulation of damage trails (fission tracks) left from fragments produced by the spontaneous nuclear fission of ²³⁸U in natural minerals and glasses. Since the first experiments performed by Price and Walker (1962), the method has developed very fast and, during the last decades, FT analysis has become a widespread approach for reconstruction of the thermal history of rocks from the shallow levels of the Earth’s crust at temperatures generally between 60 °C and 300 °C. Some of the most used applications of FT analysis include reconstruction of time-temperature history of rocks, estimation of denudation/exhumation rates of mountain chains, dating of faults and ore minerali-

zations, deciphering sedimentary basin evolution, as well as dating volcanic deposits. The most used minerals in FT analysis are apatite and zircon applied for studying the geological evolution of rocks at temperatures from 60 °C to 120 °C (Donelick *et al.*, 2005) and between 230 °C and 310 °C (Tagami *et al.*, 1998), respectively. The unique advantage of the FT method is that it can give information not only on maximum temperatures attained by the analyzed rocks (closure temperature concept), but also their variation through time, between 120 °C and 60 °C, using modeling of the apatite FT age and track length distribution (Donelick *et al.*, 2005).

Two different approaches have been used for FT analysis. An earlier FT dating method (conventional external detector method) requires a thermal neutron irradiation of the samples to produce induced fission tracks of ²³⁵U in external detectors (*e.g.*,

mica) attached to the mineral surfaces, which is used as a proxy for ^{238}U contents (Tagami and Sullivan, 2005, and references therein). In the last 20 years, a new method has successfully been applied using Laser Ablation-Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) in order to determine directly the ^{238}U content in the studied apatite and zircon grains (Cox *et al.*, 2000; Svojtka and Kosieler, 2002; Hasebe *et al.*, 2004), and thus avoiding the neutron irradiation, as well as the handling of radioactive materials.

FIRST ATTEMPTS TO APPLY FISSION-TRACK ANALYSIS IN BULGARIA

The first attempts to apply FT dating in Bulgaria were made in the 1980s when some experimental dating of micas (muscovite and biotite) from the Rhodope and Sredna Gora zones were performed (Kashukeev *et al.*, 1979; Arnaudov, 1980; Monchev, 1984, 1985). At that time, FT analysis was not so advanced, and the closure temperature of the method and notions of partially annealing zone were still not well constrained. Therefore, the younger FT ages compared to the previously obtained from the same samples K-Ar ages were explained simply by some later heating events and migration of ^{238}U . Some attempts were made also to correct these ages in order to obtain the absolute ages of the dated rocks (Monchev, 1984). Despite the relatively limited success of these first FT experiments, they could be considered as a first step in the revelation of the importance of the Late Alpine processes in the evolution of the Rhodope and Sredna Gora zones. Unfortunately, the method was not applied in Bulgaria during the next two decades.

FISSION-TRACK ANALYSIS – CONVENTIONAL METHOD

In the last twenty years, a large number of FT studies have brought several advances in the better understanding of the Alpine tectonic evolution of Bulgaria. For the first time, some quantitative estimates were provided on the exhumation rates, as well as thermotectonic evolution of different geological units. Particular success was achieved in the estimation of the time frame and exhumation rates of processes related to the crustal extension in the Cenozoic. Often, best results were obtained when FT analyses were combined with some other low-temperature thermochronological methods (*e.g.*,

(U-Th)/He and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$) together with detailed structural analysis.

Below, a short review is provided of the main FT results obtained from different studies dedicated to the geological evolution of several tectonic zones in Bulgaria during the last twenty years.

Kraishte Zone

The tectonic evolution of the Kraishte Zone during the Early Alpine orogeny was related to the thrusting of the Vlasina-Morava Unit onto the Struma Unit (*e.g.*, Kounov *et al.*, 2010; see also Fig. 1). The FT data from different structural domains of the Vlasina-Morava thrust sheet and its footwall, the Struma Unit, constrain the Cretaceous tectonothermal evolution of this structure (Kounov *et al.*, 2010). In this case, low-temperature thermochronological analyses revealed the time interval of the main thrusting event (136–112 Ma), as well as the original thickness and extent of the thrust sheet (Fig. 1). Varying zircon FT ages along the footwall and hanging wall of the thrust defined different structural levels associated with the thermal evolution during this major tectonic event in the area (Kounov *et al.*, 2010). Late Cretaceous zircon FT ages from the footwalls of a series of low-angle normal faults in the Kraishte Zone attested to post-orogenic extensional tectonics during this time.

The zircon and apatite FT data from the Kraishte Zone also give evidence for the first time for an extensional driven cooling between 47 Ma and 32 Ma, which led to the exhumation of the Crnook-Osogovo-Lisets Complex along a system of detachment faults (Fig. 1; Kounov *et al.*, 2004, 2010; Antić *et al.*, 2016). The younging direction of the FT ages further indicates that the bulk movement along the main detachment fault was top-to-the-SW (Kounov *et al.*, 2004). Thermal modeling of the apatite FT data reveals a heat transfer to the hanging wall from rapidly exhuming hot core of the extensional complex (Kounov *et al.*, 2004). Tuff layers in the turbiditic deposits from the extensional basins were dated with a zircon FT method at 35 Ma. A second magmatic phase, associated with the emplacement of subvolcanic bodies and dykes cutting the detachments, suggests that, at the beginning of the Oligocene, the detachments became inactive. These igneous rocks yielded zircon FT and U-Pb ages between 32 Ma and 29 Ma (Kounov *et al.*, 2004). Zircon and apatite FT and zircon U-Pb analysis from the Osogovo granite yielded identical age of 31 Ma, suggesting a very fast cooling of the pluton after its emplacement to temperatures below $\sim 110^\circ\text{C}$ (Kounov *et al.*, 2004).

Fig. 1. Tectonic map of Bulgaria with time ranges of the main tectonically induced heating (red) and cooling (blue) events in different tectonic zones as constrained from the published low-temperature thermochronological analyses. WRMC – Western Rhodope metamorphic complex; SRMC – Southern Rhodope metamorphic complex; CRMC – Central Rhodope metamorphic complex; ERMC – Eastern Rhodope metamorphic complex; PB – Panagyurishte Basin; PP – Plovdiv pluton; ViT – Vidlich thrust; VrT – Vratsa thrust; SBGS – Sub-Balkan graben system; BVT – Botev Vrah thrust.

Central Balkan Zone

Balkanska *et al.* (2012, 2015a) and Kounov *et al.* (2018) presented the first thermochronological constraints on the tectonic evolution of the central part of the Balkan Zone. Based on zircon and apatite FT data, they were able to provide some estimates on the time of the Early and Late Alpine thrusting events in the area. Age-altitude plot of the zircon FT data from the autochthon of the Botev Vrah thrust suggests some post-tectonic cooling and denudation between ~121 Ma and ~118 Ma, postdating the Early Alpine thrusting, during which the whole area was at temperatures higher than 250 °C (Fig. 1; Balkanska *et al.*, 2015a).

Concerning the Late Alpine tectonics, the modeling of the apatite FT and He data show a period of relatively fast cooling from ~58 Ma to ~48 Ma, which could be tentatively attributed to rapid uplift and denudation during the compression (Fig. 1; Kounov *et al.*, 2018). These data corroborate well the youngest zircon FT age obtained from the allochthon of the Late Alpine thrust (54±3 Ma) interpreted as related to cooling induced by exhumation during the early stages of the thrusting (Balkanska *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, the lower-middle Eocene (56.0–37.8 Ma) sandstones near Gabrovo yielded zircon FT detrital population ages of 68±6 Ma and 46±8 Ma. The fact that the younger population overlaps with the depositional age of the sediments

suggests a very fast exhumation of the advancing thrust wedge sourcing the basin at ~46 Ma (Kounov *et al.*, 2018).

Kounov *et al.* (2018) reported apatite FT combined with (U-Th)/He analyses revealing at least two extensional denudation phases during the Cenozoic in the central part of the Balkan Zone. The first extensional phase took place between ~44 Ma and 30 Ma and was related to the syn- to post-orogenic collapse or back-arc extension coeval with the earliest Cenozoic extensional stage observed across the southern Balkan Peninsula (Fig. 1). A period of relative quiescence (between ~30 Ma and ~25 Ma) was followed by the next cooling stage, between 25 Ma and 20 Ma, which appears to be related to a late Oligocene to early Miocene crustal extension. Extension accommodated by the late Miocene to recent age Sub-Balkan graben system does not appear to have produced exhumation of rocks from beneath 2–4 km depth, as it was not detected by the low-temperature thermochronological methods (Fig. 1; Kounov *et al.*, 2018).

Rhodope Zone

The FT analyses, combined with other low- and high-temperature geochronological methods, and coupled with detailed structural studies, revealed the complex thermotectonic evolution of the Rhodope metamorphic complex during the Cenozoic. Being part of the Aegean region, the Rhodope Zone was under extensional tectonic regime during a large part of the Cenozoic. The extension in the Rhodope Zone started already in the middle Eocene and was associated with the formation of metamorphic core complexes exhumed along a system of detachment faults. The extension was accompanied by volcanism and deposition of terrigenous sediments in fault-controlled basins.

A combination of previously published U–Pb, Rb–Sr, and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ studies on various minerals with new titanite, zircon and apatite FT, and apatite (U–Th)/He analyses from the Central Rhodope metamorphic complex, indicated that partial melting between 47 Ma and 37 Ma was followed by very fast cooling and exhumation from >650 °C to 60 °C between ~37 Ma and ~33 Ma along a series of ductile-to-brittle low-angle extensional shear zones (Fig. 1; Kounov *et al.*, 2020). Similar results were obtained from a combination of FT and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ analysis from the Western and Southern Rhodope metamorphic complexes where the extension was associated with amphibolite- to greenschist-facies rock exhumation along the North Rhodopean (39–35 Ma) and

Kerdilion (42–24 Ma) detachments, respectively (Fig. 1; Danišik *et al.*, 2014; Gunell *et al.*, 2017; Calvet *et al.*, 2015; Kounov *et al.*, 2015, 2023). Low-temperature thermochronological methods allowed extremely high exhumation rates of about 5 km/Ma for the Central Rhodope metamorphic complex to 7 km/Ma for the Western Rhodope (north slopes of the Rila Mountains) to be calculated for the Eocene extension (Kounov *et al.*, 2020, 2023). Magmatic activity in the Oligocene (33–29 Ma) may have led to a spatially irregular elevation of the geothermal gradient and, consequently, reset some of the FT data in the Central and Eastern Rhodope metamorphic complexes (Márton *et al.*, 2010; Kounov *et al.*, 2020).

A second extensional phase from the late Oligocene to the early Miocene (24–12 Ma) was documented by the FT and (U–Th)/He data from the Central and Southern Rhodope metamorphic complexes, controlled in the latter by the Strymon Valley detachment (Fig. 1; Kounov *et al.*, 2015, 2020). Additionally, the FT analysis from the northern Rila Mountains gave some evidence of a heating event during the early Miocene, probably related to strike-slip and thrust tectonics (Danišik *et al.*, 2014; Kounov *et al.*, 2023).

The third, mid–late Miocene–Quaternary (15–0 Ma) extensional phase, is associated with movements along brittle, steeply dipping normal faults, which control the formation of extensional sedimentary basins in their hanging walls along the Western and Southern Rhodope metamorphic complexes (Fig. 1; Danišik *et al.*, 2014; Gunell *et al.*, 2017; Calvet *et al.*, 2015; Kounov *et al.*, 2015, 2023). This extension continues even in the Quaternary, shown by the continuous sedimentation in the basins bordering the Rila and Pirin mountains and led to the development of high local relief.

Strandzha Zone

Cattò *et al.* (2018) provided the first low-temperature thermochronological results for the Strandzha massif, based on apatite FT analysis of Permian, Triassic, and Cretaceous rock samples. Their analyses clearly showed that the massif has escaped significant post-Jurassic deformation and metamorphism. Thermal modeling of the apatite FT data reveals that the central part of the massif experienced a Late Jurassic heating followed by a Kimmeridgian–Berriasian phase of relatively rapid cooling and very slow cooling in Cretaceous to early Eocene times (Fig. 1). These results are consistent with a Late Jurassic–Early Cretaceous phase of north-verging thrust-

ing and regional metamorphism, followed by very slow cooling/exhumation driven by post-orogenic erosion in the area. Modeling of samples from the northern sector of the Strandzha massif constrains a phase of cooling in the middle–late Eocene, probably associated with an important phase of shortening recorded in the East Balkan fold-and-thrust belt.

FISSION-TRACK ANALYSIS USING LA-ICP-MS

The first FT results from the Balkan Zone using LA-ICP-MS were obtained in Kyoto and Kanazawa Universities, Japan (Balkanska *et al.*, 2015b). In the last five years, many of the advances in the interpretation of the Bulgarian geology using the FT analysis have been related to the establishment of the Low-Temperature Thermochronological Laboratory in the Department of Geology, Paleontology and Fossil Fuels (Sofia University) and the Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The lab was formed and is working in a close collaboration with the colleagues from Kyoto University, Japan. The newly adopted procedures of preparation and processing of apatite and zircon samples for FT analysis using LA-ICP-MS are described in Balkanska *et al.* (2017, 2021b). The first FT results obtained in the new laboratory contributed mainly to the better understanding of the Alpine evolution and exhumation history of the Sredna Gora Zone. Currently, the lab is actively involved in the acquisition of the first FT results from the Eastern Rhodope metamorphic complex and Antarctica.

Western Balkan Zone

The first low-temperature thermochronological results from the western part of the Balkan Zone were reported by Balkanska *et al.* (2015b). The apatite and zircon FT analysis of Permian to Lower Cretaceous sediments and Carboniferous magmatic rocks gave some constraints on the Alpine tectonic evolution of the area. Thermal modeling of the apatite FT data from the autochthon of the Vidlich thrust suggests Early Alpine age of some of the displacements along this structure (Fig. 1). The apatite FT age of 47.8 ± 4.7 Ma from the hanging wall of the Vratsa thrust is probably related to cooling after the Late Alpine thrusting in the area.

Sredna Gora Zone

Balkanska *et al.* (2022a) reported the first apatite and zircon FT results providing constraints on the Alpine thermal and tectonic evolution of the Sredna

Gora Zone. They studied Late Carboniferous–Permian granitoids from the pre-Alpine basement, together with Upper Cretaceous volcanic and subvolcanic rocks and Upper Maastrichtian–Danian conglomerates from the Panagyurishte Basin (Fig. 1). The FT analysis, combined with $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating, revealed several post-Triassic heating and cooling episodes in the central parts of the Sredna Gora Zone. The results showed that a Late Cretaceous arc-related magmatic activity induced an elevated thermal gradient and reheating of the basement rocks and the overlying sediments and volcanics from the Panagyurishte Basin at temperatures above $\sim 250 \pm 50$ °C. The modeling of apatite FT data gives evidence for a middle to late Paleocene thermal event between 65 Ma and 55 Ma, possibly related to the Late Alpine thrusting and closure of the Panagyurishte back-/intra-arc basin, during which the tectonically buried sediments attained a temperature of < 120 °C (Fig. 1). This event was followed by rapid to moderate cooling of the sedimentary and volcanic successions at 55–50 Ma, probably during syn-tectonic erosion and denudation of the thrust sheets. The apatite FT analysis of the Late Carboniferous–Permian granitoids indicated that the exhumation of the crystalline basement took place during one or two stages of post-orogenic middle Eocene to Oligocene extension, most probably related to the opening of the Thrace Basin (Fig. 1). Balkanska *et al.* (2021a) reported the first quantitative estimates on the exhumation rates of 0.46 mm/year from the basement rocks.

The thermal and tectonic evolution of the Plovdiv pluton in the southern part of the Sredna Gora Zone was revealed by apatite and zircon FT analysis, combined with $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating (Fig. 1; Balkanska *et al.*, 2022b). The zircon FT age of the pluton suggested cooling below $\sim 250 \pm 50$ °C in the early Eocene that could be related to a thermal relaxation following the regional early Eocene magmatic pulse in the Rhodope Zone or a post-orogenic cooling following the middle to late Paleocene Late Alpine compression in the Sredna Gora Zone. The thermal modeling of apatite FT data reveals very fast cooling to ~ 90 °C between 44 Ma and 42 Ma, interpreted as a period of denudation and extension associated with the formation of the Thrace Basin (Fig. 1).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The important thermochronological results obtained in the last 20 years from several tectonic zones in Bulgaria clearly demonstrate the signifi-

cance of FT analysis in deciphering the thermal and tectonic evolution of the Balkanides. Quantitative estimates on the exhumation rates and the thermotectonic processes in the Kraishite, Balkan, Sredna Gora, Strandzha and Rhodope zones contributed to considerable advances in the understanding of the geological evolution of these areas.

The key to the success is the combination of FT analysis with some other low- and high-temperature geochronological methods, coupled with detailed structural and petrological analysis. Therefore, we are looking further to the acquisition of more multidisciplinary studies on the evolution of some other regions of Bulgaria and probably refinement of our knowledge from already studied zones.

The broad application of the thermochronological methods worldwide will increase the interest of FT analysis in the future and will incontestably lead to resolving various geological issues and problems. The established new Low-Temperature Thermochronological Laboratory is a good premise for the future development of fission-track analysis in Bulgaria.

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